

STUDIES ON 2-AMINOBENZTHIAZOLES

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2-Aminobenzthiazoles have been synthesised by condensing *as*-arylthioureas with bromine in chloroform, and their properties and group reactions leading to various derivatives have been studied.

Hugershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3121) prepared 2-aminobenzthiazoles by the action of liquid bromine on asymmetrical phenylthiourea in chloroform. Hunter *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2023; 1926, 1385) studied the conditions for the formation of alkyl-substituted 2-aminobenzthiazoles and showed that in these compounds tautomerism was exhibited by the mobility of the symmetrical triad system, as verified by symmetry test (Ingold and Piggot, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2381) and substitution test (Farrow and Ingold, *ibid.*, 1924, 126, 2543). Kaufmann and Schubert (U. S. P., 1,787,315; 1,787,316) and Kaufmann *et al.* (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1928, 266 215) studied substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles, prepared by the thiocyanation of *para*-substituted aromatic amines in acid solution. Brewster and Dains (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1364) prepared several thiazoles by the cupric thiocyanate method and found that thiocyanation did not occur in compounds containing acetamido or carbethoxyamino groups. It was therefore considered worthwhile, in view of their medicinal importance as local anaesthetics, to prepare ten 2-aminobenzthiazoles (I) by the method of Hugershoff (*loc. cit.*) from ten different *as*-arylthioureas, obtained by the well-known method of De Clermont (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 70) and also that of Berkebile and Fries (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1948, 28, 618).

The $-NH_2$ group in the compounds, being considered full of utility for the preparation of derivatives, has been acetylated and benzoylated in a few cases only, yielding 2-acetylamino- and 2-benzoylamino-benzthiazoles.

The process of diazotisation of the free $-NH_2$ group and subsequent coupling with alkaline β -naphthol to form azo- β -naphthol derivatives have been found to be more difficult with increase in substitution in the benzene nucleus. Thus, only five of the ten thiazoles have yielded well-defined azo- β -naphthol derivatives.

Further, considering from the practical point of view that paper, impregnated with 2-aminobenzthiazoles, is used in legal documents or cheques as safety paper because ink eradicators, which usually contain sodium hypochlorite, develop a red coloured blot almost instantaneously when applied. An attempt has been made to substantiate the course of this reaction with sodium hypochlorite in the case of all

the ten benzthiazoles according to Kirk *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1943, 8, 557), when coloured 2:2'-dibenzo-azothiazoles (II) have been obtained.

These azo compounds exhibit characteristic colour in glacial acetic acid, thus showing the nature of a dye. A confirmation of the constitution of these azo compounds has been corroborated by the results of the estimation of —N=N— group and isolation and identification by the mixed m.p. of the corresponding original 2-aminobenzthiazoles from them by reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid and subsequently adding ammonia till alkaline.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Aminobenzthiazole.—*o*-Phenylthiourea (10 g.), suspended in dry chloroform (25 c.c.), was gradually treated with liquid bromine (6 c.c.) in dry chloroform (50 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath till no more HBr had evolved. The solid was filtered free of the solvent, dried, suspended in sulphurous acid solution, and sulphur dioxide gas was passed till a clear solution was obtained. It was filtered and treated with ammonia till alkaline. The precipitated 2-aminobenzthiazole was filtered, washed, dried and finally crystallised from hot rectified spirit in a white crystalline form, m.p. 129°, yield 7.5 g.

Similarly other 2-aminobenzthiazoles were prepared. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

2-Aminobenzthiazoles.

[B denotes benzthiazoles. A denotes 2-Amino-].

Compounds.	% Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% S or halogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. A-B ¹	75	129°	C ₇ H ₆ N ₂ S	18.12	18.66	20.98	21.33
2. A-chloro-B	70	202°	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ ClS	15.39	15.18	18.98	19.24
3. A-6-bromo-B ²	80	212°	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ BrS	12.42	12.24	34.62*	34.90
4. A- <i>o</i> -nitro-B ³	65	161°	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	20.98	21.54	15.92*	16.41
5. A-4-methyl-B ²	75	136°	C ₈ H ₆ N ₂ S	17.48	17.68	19.12	19.51
6. A-5-methyl-B	74	143°	C ₈ H ₆ N ₂ S	17.52	17.68	19.24	19.51
7. A-6-methoxy-B ⁴	70	146°	C ₈ H ₈ ON ₂ S	15.28	15.55	16.98	17.77
8. A-6-ethoxy-B ⁴	72	173°	C ₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	14.08	14.43	15.98	16.49
9. A- α -naphthothiazole ²	50	250°	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ S	13.85	14.00	15.75	16.00
10. A- β -naphthothiazole ²	70	238°	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ S	14.33	14.00	15.62	16.00

* Refers to halogen.

1. Hegershoff, *loc. cit.*

2. Hunter *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1926.

3. " *loc. cit.*, 1925.

4. " *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1186.

2-Acetylaminobenzthiazole.—2-Aminobenzthiazole (1 g.) was heated under reflux with acetic anhydride (4 c.c.), cooled and poured into water. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from hot water, m.p. 186°.

Similarly the acetyl derivatives of some other thiazoles were prepared. The number of acetyl group in these derivatives was found to be one on analysis. The acetylation was not successful in the case of 2-amino-5-ethoxybenzthiazole, - α -naphthothiazole and - β -naphthothiazole. The properties and analyses are reported in Table II.

2-Benzoylaminobenzthiazole.—2-Aminobenzthiazole was benzoylated as usual into a colorless form, m.p. 184°. Similarly other thiazoles were benzoylated and the number of benzoyl group on analysis was found to be one. The benzoylation was not successful with 2-amino-6-methoxybenzthiazole, -6-ethoxybenzthiazole, - α -naphthothiazole and - β -naphthothiazole. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds.	Acetyl derivative.			Benzoyl derivative.		
	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen Found. Calc.
1.	186°	C ₉ H ₉ ON ₂ S*	14.62 14.58	184°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S*	11.10 11.02
2.	289°	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ ClS	12.40 12.35	286°	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	9.26 9.70
3.	223°	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ BrS	10.38 10.33	203°	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ BrS	8.44 8.40
4.	286°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₃ N ₂ S	17.90 17.72	203°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ S	14.88 14.84
5.	252°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	13.62 13.59	221°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	10.40 10.44
6.	224°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	13.52 13.59	206°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	10.72 10.44
7.	210°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	12.69 12.62	...	...	...

* Hunter *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1926.

N.B. The number corresponds to those in Table I.

Benzthiazole-2-azo- β -naphthol.—2-Aminobenzthiazole (1.5 g.), suspended in HCl (dil., 20 c.c.), was diazotised as usual. The product was coupled with β -naphthol (1.4 g.), dissolved in 5% NaOH solution (8 c.c.). The orange-brown azo compound on extraction with ether and crystallisation in vacuum gave purple-red crystals, m.p. 147°. Similarly four other thiazoles formed 2-azo- β -naphthol derivatives, but diazotisation and coupling with the rest five failed, as recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

*2-Azo- β -naphthol derivatives of	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
No. 1.	Purple-red	147°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S	13.82	13.77
2.	Brownish red	232°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClS	12.41	12.37
5.	Red	172°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	13.22	13.16
9.	Chocolate	276°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	11.89	11.83
10.	Brownish red	192°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	11.92	11.83

2:2'-Dibenzo-azothiazole.—2-Aminobenzthiazole (1 g.) in water (30 c.c.) was gradually treated with 0.3 N sodium hypochlorite solution (50 c.c.). The purple

precipitate, produced after being washed with ether, separated from a mixture of chloroform and light petroleum ether (1:1) at 20° as dark purple crystals, m.p. 159°. It developed a yellow colour in glacial acetic acid. Similarly other substituted dibenzo-azothiazoles were prepared. The properties and analytical data are mentioned in Table IV.

TABLE IV
[D denotes dibenzo-azothiazole]

Azothiazoles.	Colour.	M.P.	Colour AcOH.	Formula,	% -N=N-	
					Found.	Calc.
2:2'-D-	Purple	159°	Yellow	$C_{14}H_8N_4S_2$	9.382	9.461
2:2'-4:4'-Dichloro-D	Black	214°	Do	$C_{14}H_6N_4Cl_2S_2$	7.722	7.672
2:2'-6:6'-Dibromo-D	Do	290°	Orange	$C_{14}H_6N_4Br_2S_2$	6.202	6.170
2:2'-6:6'-Dinitro-D	Brown	142°	Orange-red	$C_{14}H_6O_4N_6S_2$	7.312	7.291
2:2'-4:4'-Dimethyl-D	Pink	228°	Red	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4S_2$	8.524	8.644
2:2'-5:5'-Dimethyl-D	Brown	174°	Dark red	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4S_2$	8.723	8.644
2:2'-6:6'-Dimethoxy-D	Black	122°	Blood-red	$C_{18}H_{12}O_2N_4S_2$	7.872	7.866
2:2'-6:6'-Diethoxy-D	Black	136°	Crimson	$C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_4S_2$	7.188	7.293
2:2'-Di- α -naphtho-	Pink	212°	Violet	$C_{22}H_{12}N_4S_2$	6.982	7.071
2:2'-Di- β -naphtho-	Black	194°	Red	$C_{22}H_{12}N_4S_2$	7.123	7.071

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